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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****FORMULATION AND INVITRO EVALUATION OF FAST
DISINTEGRATING TABLETS OF AN ANTI-INFLAMMATORY
DRUG**

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Article Received: March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:**

Oral disintegrating tablets are defined as the tablets that disperse or disintegrate in less than one minute in the mouth prior to being swallowed, which results in the rapid dissolution and absorption of the active pharmaceutical ingredient contained in the tablet, providing rapid onset of action. Aceclofenac is a poorly water-soluble drug. The solubility of the drug was enhanced by solid dispersion technique using mannitol as the carrier. In the present study, 9 formulations were developed by using different super disintegrants like cross povidone, sodium starchglycolate and cross carmellose sodium in various ratios. The tablets were prepared by direct compression method and evaluated for precompression parameters like bulk density, tapped density, angle of repose, compressibility index, Hausner's ratio, and post-compression parameters like hardness, friability, drug content, disintegration, and dissolution. The results were found to be satisfactory. Tablets which were prepared by cross povidone 5% (F9 formulation) showed the best results. The percentage of drug release was found to be 98.23% at 30 minutes and disintegration time was found to be 17 seconds.

Keywords: Oral disintegrating tablets, aceclofenac, solid dispersions, super disintegrants.

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INTRODUCTION:

Fast disintegrating tablets (FDTs) have received ever-increasing demand during the last decade, and the field has become a rapidly growing area in the pharmaceutical industry. Oral drug delivery remains the preferred route for administration of various drugs. Recent developments in technology have prompted scientists to develop FDTs with improved patient compliance and convenience. Upon introduction into the mouth, these tablets dissolve or disintegrate in the mouth in the absence of additional water for easy administration of active pharmaceutical ingredients. FDTs or orally disintegrating tablets provide an advantage particularly for pediatric and geriatric populations who have difficulty in swallowing conventional tablets and capsules [1]. Aceclofenac is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug used in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis, osteoarthritis, and spondylitis. The recommended dose is 100mg twice daily. It works by blocking actions of cyclooxygenase enzyme [2]. In the present study, an attempt was made to increase the solubility of aceclofenac by using solid dispersion technique using mannitol as a carrier

and to prepare the tablets with various super disintegrating agents like sodium starch glycolate, croscarmellose sodium and Crospovidone in different concentrations by using direct compression method.

MATERIALS & METHODS:**Materials:**

Aceclofenac drug was obtained as a gift sample by Micro labs Bangalore. Cross carmellose sodium, sodium starch glycolate, and Crospovidone, was obtained from S.D. FINE chemicals, Mumbai. All the excipients used were of analytical grade.

Pre-formulation Studies**Compatibility Studies:**

Infrared spectra of pure drug and mixture of drug and excipients were recorded by Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer [3] (Shimadzu, Japan). In the present study, drug and superdisintegrants were mixed with KBr and compressed into pellets and the samples were analyzed in the scanning range of 4000-400cm⁻¹.

Fig.1: FT-IR of Aceclofenac with cross povidone

Fig. 2: FT-IR of Aceclofenac with mannitol

Formulation of Aceclofenac FDT

Solid dispersions containing aceclofenac with mannitol was prepared in the ratio of 1:2 by solvent melt method. In this method, aceclofenac was dissolved in acetone and the solution was incorporated into the melt of mannitol at 165⁰ C by pouring into it. It was kept in an ice bath for sudden cooling. The mass was kept in the desiccators for complete drying. The solidified mass was scrapped, crushed, pulverized and passed through 80 sieves.

Aceclofenac fast dissolving tablets were prepared using direct compression method. Aceclofenac and mannitol mixture was mixed separately with Sodium starch glycolate, croscarmellose sodium, and crospovidone with concentrations of 1%, 3%, and 5% respectively. The above blend was mixed with sweetening agents and finally glidant, lubricant was added and compressed into tablets using compression machine⁵. 20 tablets of each 9 formulations were prepared, which were mentioned in table 1.

Table.1: Formulation of Aceclofenac fast dissolving tablets:

S.no	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1	Amount of Solid dispersions equivalent to 100 mg of the drug	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
2	Sodium Starch Glycolate	5	15	25	---	---	---	---	---	--
3	Croscarmellose Sodium	---	---	---	5	15	25	---	---	---
4	Crospovidone	---	---	---	---	---	---	5	15	25
5	Microcrystalline Cellulose	170	160	150	170	160	150	170	160	150
6	Sodium lauryl Sulfate	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
7	Sodium saccharin	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
8	Magnesium stearate	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
9	Talc	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
10	Total tab weight	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500

Evaluation of the tablets**Pre-compression parameters:**

1. Bulk density: The bulk density is a measure used to describe packing materials or granule. It was determined by transferring the accurately weighed amount of powder sample to the 100ml graduated cylinder. The initial volume was noted and the ratio of the weight of the sample to the volume it occupied was calculated [6].

2. Tapped density: Weighed powder sample was transferred to a graduated cylinder and was placed on the tapped density test apparatus, was operated for a fixed number of taps (100). The tapped density was determined as the ratio of the weight of the sample to tapped volume [7].

Tapped Density = Mass / Tapped Volume

3. Hausner's Ratio: The ratio of tapped density to the bulk density of the powders is called the Hausner's ratio⁷.

Hausner Ratio= tapped density/bulk density

4. Carr's Index (% Compressibility): Based on the apparent bulk and tapped density, the percentage compressibility of the bulk drug was determined by using the following formula [7].

% Compressibility = Tapped density – Bulk density / Tapped density*100

5. The angle of Repose: The angle of repose was determined by the funnel method suggested by Newman. Approximately 5gm of powder was poured through a glass funnel from a height of 6 centimeters onto a level bench top. The angle that the side of the conical heap made with the horizontal plane was recorded as the angle of repose. The angle of repose is determined by the following formula [8].

Tan θ = h/r

Where θ = Angle of repose h and r are the height and radius of the powder cone.

Table.2: Evaluation of Precompression parameters.

Formulation	Angle of repose (°) ±SD*	Compressibility index(%) ±SD*	Hausner ratio ±SD*
F1	26.98±0.03	13.45±0.042	1.13±0.045
F2	25.12±0.04	12.65±0.041	1.12±0.035
F3	24.53±0.05	12.85±0.065	1.18±0.045
F4	25.65±0.04	14.08±0.07	1.16±0.041
F5	24.63±0.045	14.75±0.02	1.00±0.032
F6	24.23±0.055	14.28±0.04	1.14±0.033
F7	26.43±0.035	15.88±0.03	1.13±0.47
F8	27.35±0.35	15.76±0.03	1.11±0.05
F9	24.04±0.25	13.98±0.04	1.09±0.039

Post-compression parameters:**1. Hardness:**

The crushing strength of the tablets was measured using Pfizer hardness tester. Tablets from each formulation batch were tested randomly by placing the tablet was placed in contact between the plungers, and the handle was pressed, the force of the fracture was recorded and the average reading was noted⁹. The hardness is measured in kg/cm².

2. Thickness:

The thickness of tablets from each batch was recorded during the process of compression using vernier calipers [9].

3. Friability:

Ten tablets were weighed and placed in a Roche Friabilator and the equipment was rotated at 25 rpm for 4 min. The tablets were taken out, de-dusted and reweighed. And the percentage of friability was calculated using the following formula [10]:

$$F = (1 - W_0 / W) \times 100$$

Table.3: Post-compression parameters of F1 – F9 formulations

Formulation	Hardness ±SD (kg/cm ²)	Friability % ± SD	Average weight ±SD (mg)	Disintegration time ±SD (in secs)	Drug content (%) ±SD
F1	4.8±0.16	0.58±0.03	493± 0.16	43± 0.07	99.0±0.14
F2	4.6±0.18	0.65±0.05	497± 0.18	35±0.04	98.3±0.17
F3	4.7±0.25	0.49±0.02	496± 0.21	30± 0.15	98.9±0.18
F4	4.8±0.05	0.68±0.04	494± 0.15	50±0.05	99.4±0.12
F5	4.5±0.05	0.58±0.03	492± 0.19	40±0.02	98.7±0.15
F6	4.8±0.15	0.67±0.05	493±0.15	35±0.03	97.6±0.14
F7	4.7±0.12	0.65±0.04	498± 0.30	29±0.30	99.5±0.13
F8	4.8±0.13	0.64±0.04	495± 0.10	20±0.15	97.3±0.15
F9	4.8±0.15	0.67±0.05	499± 0.15	17±0.05	98.9±0.14

Where W₀ is the weight of the tablets before the test and W is the weight of the tablet after the test.

4. Estimation of drug content:

For drug content analysis ten tablets were accurately weighed and finely powdered. Quantity of powder equivalent to 100 mg of aceclofenac was taken into a 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in phosphate buffer pH 6.8. 5 ml of the filtrate was diluted to 100 ml by phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and analyzed for drug content at 275.0 nm using double beam UV/Vis. Spectrophotometer [10].

5. In vitro disintegration time

The disintegration of tablets was determined using a USP disintegration testing apparatus using phosphate buffer as a disintegrating medium. The medium was maintained at 37±0.5 °C throughout the test. Six tablets were placed into an apparatus and disintegration time was recorded [11]. The results were tabulated in Table -3.

6. In vitro dissolution studies:

The drug release was determined using USP standard dissolution tester, Apparatus II rotating paddle (ElectrolabTDT-08L, India). Dissolution was carried out in 900 ml of phosphate buffer at pH 6.8. The paddle was rotated at 50 rpm at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Aliquots of 5 ml were withdrawn and replaced with equal volumes of fresh phosphate buffer pH 6.8 at specified time intervals. Samples were adequately diluted, filtered through a $0.22 \mu\text{m}$ filter and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 275nm [12,13].

Table.4: Cumulative Percentage drug release:

Time in minutes	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	14.2 \pm 0.15	23.86 \pm 0.11	31.25 \pm 0.08	8.2 \pm 0.18	12.6 \pm 0.15	19.07 \pm 0.18	21.74 \pm 0.12	24.08 \pm 0.10	26.23 \pm 0.14
10	23.67 \pm 0.16	38.32 \pm 0.15	42.06 \pm 0.14	13.67 \pm 0.16	22.54 \pm 0.16	29.48 \pm 0.19	41.92 \pm 0.16	52.67 \pm 0.09	54.48 \pm 0.14
15	45.72 \pm 0.18	52.25 \pm 0.18	58.86 \pm 0.10	23.72 \pm 0.09	33.97 \pm 0.14	44.28 \pm 0.17	53.97 \pm 0.12	61.88 \pm 0.18	68.94 \pm 0.10
20	56.21 \pm 0.16	68.95 \pm 0.16	72.07 \pm 0.14	40.2 \pm 0.10	47.45 \pm 0.12	61.56 \pm 0.18	71.06 \pm 0.14	74.97 \pm 0.09	79.23 \pm 0.16
25	63.65 \pm 0.14	75.57 \pm 0.16	81.52 \pm 0.16	57.65 \pm 0.12	65.82 \pm 0.09	71.2 \pm 0.18	82.99 \pm 0.18	87.62 \pm 0.09	90.02 \pm 0.16
30	71.83 \pm 0.16	82.44 \pm 0.18	89.27 \pm 0.18	68.2 \pm 0.12	73.48 \pm 0.12	80.26 \pm 0.18	90.33 \pm 0.16	94.02 \pm 0.14	98.23 \pm 0.14

Fig.6: In vitro drug release of F1-F4 formulations

Fig.7: *In vitro* drug release of F5-F9 formulations

Fig. 8: Zero order kinetics of F1 – F4 formulations

Fig. 9: Zero order kinetics of F5 – F9 formulations

Fig.10: First order kinetics of F1 – F4 formulations

Fig.11: First order kinetics of F5 – F9 formulations

Table.5: R² values for zero order and first order release kinetics:

Formulation Code	R ² Value	
	Zero order	First Order
F1	0.967	0.988
F2	0.946	0.962
F3	0.956	0.981
F4	0.940	0.969
F5	0.928	0.950
F6	0.923	0.956
F7	0.948	0.959
F8	0.929	0.963
F9	0.912	0.992

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Preformulation studies:

A physical mixture of drug and excipients was characterized by FTIR spectral analysis for any physical as well as chemical alteration of the drug characteristics. All the formulations are kept for spectral analysis are in the range of (5 - 30 μ /ml) and they are following Beer's Lambert's law. From the results, it was concluded that there was no interference in the functional groups as the principle peaks of the aceclofenac were found to be unaltered in the spectra of the drug-polymer physical mixture.

Evaluation of Precompression Parameters:

Pre-compression parameters like bulk density, tapped density, Hausner ratio, compressibility index and angle of repose were performed for all formulations.

The angle of Repose: The angle of repose of all formulations was found to be in the range of 24.0 – 27.35. The optimized formulation F9 shown an angle of repose 24.04 which indicates that flow property was good.

Hausner's ratio: Hausner ratio of all formulations was found to be in the range of 1.00 – 1.18. The optimized formulation F9 showed 1.09, it indicates that flow property was good.

Compressibility index: Compressibility index of all formulations was found to be in the range of 12.65 – 15.88%. The optimized formulation F9 shown 13.98% which ensures that the flow property is good.

Evaluation of post-compression parameters:

The results of post-compression parameters such as weight variation, friability, hardness, disintegration, dissolution is tabulated in table – 4.

Hardness: The hardness of each batch of tablets was found to be in the range of 4.5 – 4.8 kg/cm² which ensures good handling characteristics for all formulations and the optimized F9 formulation shown 4.8 kg/cm².

Weight variation: All the formulations passed weight variation test as the average weight of each batch of tablets was found to be in the range of 492 – 499mg. The F9 formulation has shown 499 mg.

Friability: The percentage friability was less than 0.8% for all formulations ensuring that all tablets were mechanically stable and the ranges were found between 0.59 – 0.68%. The F9 formulation shown 0.67%.

Drug content: The drug content test for all the formulations are in the range of 97.3 – 99.5%. The optimized F9 formulation shown 98.9%,

Disintegration: The formulations F1, F2, and F3 are having sodium starch glycolate in the concentrations of 1%, 3%, and 5% shown the disintegration time of 43 sec, 35 sec, and 30 sec. The formulations F4, F5, and F6 containing croscarmellose Sodium in the concentrations of 1%, 3%, and 5% shown the

disintegration time of 50 sec, 40 sec, and 35 sec. The formulations F7, F8, F9 containing crospovidone shown the disintegration time of 29 sec, 20 sec, and the F9 formulation shown disintegration time 17 seconds. An increase in the concentration of the superdisintegrant decreased the disintegration time.

In vitro dissolution:

Formulations F1, F2, and F3 containing sodium starch glycolate shown drug release of 71.27 %, 82.44%, and 89.27% respectively at the end of 30 minutes. Formulations F4, F5, and F6 containing croscarmellose sodium has shown the drug release of 68.2%, 73.48%, and 80.26 % respectively at the end of 30 minutes. The formulations F7, F8, and F9 containing Crospovidone have shown drug release of 90.33, 94.02%, 98.23% at the end of 30 minutes. Formulation F9 showed the maximum drug release of 98.23 %.

Drug release Kinetics:

The R² value of zero order kinetics of F9 formulation was found to be 0.912 and the R² value of first-order kinetics of F9 formulation was found to be 0.992. As the R² value of first-order kinetics of F9 formulation is higher than the zero-order kinetics, F9 formulation followed First order kinetics.

CONCLUSION:

Fast disintegrating tablets of Aceclofenac containing different types of super disintegrants (SSG, CP, CCS) were prepared successfully by using direct compression method. Among all the formulations, F9 showed better results i.e., percentage of drug release was found to be 98.23% in 30 minutes and disintegration time was found to be 17 seconds and can be considered as the promising formulation.

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